

Astrophysical Tau Neutrinos in IceCube

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Abstract

The IceCube Neutrino Observatory at the South Pole can detect neutrinos of all flavors well into the PeV energy range. Measuring the tau component and the overall flavor composition of astrophysical neutrinos is a powerful probe of cosmic particle accelerator mechanisms. However, due to the sparse light sensor layout and the relatively short tau decay length, tau neutrino identification in IceCube is very challenging. Despite these challenges, IceCube has successfully identified astrophysical tau neutrinos and measured the astrophysical neutrino flavor composition. After presenting the current results, I will discuss expected future improvements.

1 Introduction

The IceCube Neutrino Observatory [1] consists of a cubic kilometer of instrumented volume at the South Pole. IceCube observes atmospheric muons, atmospheric neutrinos, galactic neutrinos [2] as well as extragalactic neutrinos of all flavors [3]. The latter dominate the flux above a few tens of TeV and are observed well into the PeV energy range. The flavor composition of astrophysical neutrinos on Earth probes the environments at the cosmic sites of particle acceleration, and depends on the produced flavor composition at the source, as well as propagation effects [4] which may be altered by BSM physics [5]. While tau neutrinos are not expected to be produced in significant numbers at sources, they arise due to flavor mixing on their way to Earth [6]. In the energy ranges where the astrophysical neutrino flux dominates, atmospheric tau neutrino fluxes are negligible [7]. This makes tau neutrinos a very impactful ingredient in the study of cosmic particle accelerators.

Tau neutrino identification is, however, very challenging in IceCube: The Digital Optical Modules (DOMs) for the observation of faint Cherenkov light signals of relativistic charged particles are spaced 17 m apart vertically and 125 m apart horizontally. As neutrino flavor is typically identified by observing the charged lepton created in charged-current interactions, tau neutrino identification efficiency is limited by the tau decay length (on average ~ 50 m per PeV of energy) competing against the sparseness of the instrumentation.

2 Tau Neutrino Identification

To perform a flavor composition measurement, all three flavors of the interacting neutrinos need to be distinguished. In neutral-current (NC) interactions, the neutrino transfers some of its energy to the quark, resulting in a hadronic particle shower. The shower, or **Cascade**, is roughly spherical, but still elongated in the direction corresponding to the original neutrino. In NC interactions, the flavor of the incoming neutrino cannot be distinguished.

¹<http://icecube.wisc.edu>

Figure 1: High-energy event morphologies in IceCube: a Track, indicative of muons traversing the ice (left); a Single Cascade, created by CC electron or tau neutrinos or NC interactions of all flavors (center); and a simulated Double Bang, clear signature of a tau-neutrino interaction (right). Colored spheres indicate modules that registered light, with the size indicating the relative light yield, and the color the relative time (from red to blue). From [8].

In charged-current (CC) interactions, a secondary charged lepton is produced which can produce a distinct Cherenkov light pattern in addition to the hadronic shower at the neutrino interaction vertex. The electron has a short radiation length and produces an electromagnetic shower via bremsstrahlung. Thus, electron neutrinos create **(Single) Cascades**. High-energy muons will traverse the detector depositing stochastic energy losses along their path, creating **(Starting) Tracks**. The tau-neutrino case is the most complicated one: Given its decay length of $\langle L_\tau \rangle \approx 50 \text{ m} \cdot E/\text{PeV}$, the tau will, in most cases, decay inside the detector². If the tau decays to an electron and two neutrinos, the electron will produce an electromagnetic cascade; if the tau decays to a muon and two neutrinos, the muon will produce a track; and a tau decay producing hadrons will result in a hadronic cascade. The electronic and hadronic decays, accounting for $\approx 83\%$ of all tau decays, will produce the hadronic cascade at the neutrino interaction vertex, and a hadronic or electromagnetic cascade at the tau decay vertex. Depending on the tau decay length, the resulting signature may be a **Double Bang** [6] corresponding to two cascades that are clearly separable by eye (i.e. for $L_\tau \gg \mathcal{O}(100) \text{ m}$); a **Double Cascade** [9] if these cascades are separable algorithmically³; or a **Double Pulse** [10] if two energy depositions can be distinguished in time in the light arrival pattern on single DOMs. We consider tau-neutrino events as **Single Cascades** if the displacement between the two cascades is not observable. A visualization of the discussed high-energy morphologies in the detector is shown in Fig. 1.

As muons produce stochastic energy losses, they can produce Double Pulses, and account for the main background for tau neutrino searches using the Double Pulse method. Further, Double Pulses require the event to happen in close proximity to an optical module, as the distinct time delay in the light pattern gets washed out due to photon scattering. The main background for tau neutrino searches using the Double Cascade method are Single Cascades from electron neutrino interactions. Tau neutrinos can currently not be identified if the tau decays into a muon; however, the inelasticity distribution is sensitive to the tau content in a track sample [11]. We note that by measuring the hadronic content of the showers created in the ice via the faint, delayed Neutron Echo, IceCube would be sensitive to the neutrino flavor independent of e.g. the tau decay length [12]. However, this is very challenging experimentally, and work is ongoing to better understand late in-ice effects such as luminescence [13].

3 Recent Results and Current Status

To-date, several searches for tau neutrinos and analyses of the flavor composition have been performed in IceCube using the morphologies discussed above.

²A very high energy tau would create a track similar to a muon, but produce less light along the track due to the tau's comparatively larger radiation length.

³Currently, we use a threshold of 10 m to distinguish between single and double cascades in analyses.

Figure 2: Flavor triangle showing the neutrino flavor fractions on Earth ($f_{i,\oplus}$) with flavor composition measurements performed on the HESE [9] (dotted line) and MESE [14] (thick solid and dashed lines) samples using morphology-based event classification. Also shown are the theoretically allowed flavor composition on Earth (dash-dotted line) and a few highlighted benchmark source scenarios ($f_{i,S}$), such as the pion decay production mechanism (pink dot). From [14].

Despite candidate events, they resulted in upper limits of the astrophysical tau neutrino flux.

Beyond the Double Pulse / Double Cascade technique, an analysis utilized 2D images made from overlaying the light patterns of the modules on each of three brightest strings. A convolutional neural network was then trained to distinguish the images of tau-neutrino-induced events from other flavors. This exclusive search for tau neutrinos yielded 7 events on an expected background of 0.5, resulting in a detection of the astrophysical tau neutrino flux at $> 5\sigma$ for all tested models and astrophysical fluxes [18].

The performed analyses employ different methods. The exclusive searches filter all available data in search for signatures most compatible with a tau-neutrino hypothesis, while inclusive searches perform a classification of events that are part of an all-flavor sample rich in astrophysical neutrinos. The efficiencies for tau neutrino identification are rather low for all analyses, e.g. the Double Cascade HESE analysis has a total efficiency for tau-neutrino-induced Double Cascades of 12% for deposited energies above 60 TeV. Despite all their differences, and the low efficiencies, there is one common event in all presented analyses: A 2014 event that deposited an energy of ≈ 100 TeV in the detector, and produced a tau that decayed after traveling ≈ 17 m according to the original Double Cascade reconstruction, which also produced a Double Pulse in several optical modules. A view of this event in the detector is shown in Fig. 3.

4 Future Developments

Several new and updated analyses are currently being developed. Developments focus on the following improvements: (a) higher tau-neutrino purities from better reconstructions and filtering [19, 20]; (b) higher statistics through larger samples and higher tau-identification efficiencies [21]; (c) better modeling of in-ice shower fluctuations [19] and systematic uncertainties. One

Using the Double Cascade signature, and an algorithmic classification of High-Energy Starting Events (HESE) with 7.5 years of data [15], 2 of the 60 events were classified as Double Cascades. This analysis also fit the astrophysical flavor composition (see dotted line in Fig. 2) and the astrophysical tau neutrino flux, disfavoring its absence at the 2.8σ level. One of the Double Cascades was found to have a probability to be a tau neutrino of 98% [9].

An updated analysis using the Double Cascade signature and the classification was performed on 11.4 years of Medium-Energy Starting Events. While 9 events were classified as Double Cascades, many were in the lower-energy extension, where such high tau decay lengths are not expected. The analysis resulted in an indication of the tau neutrino flux at 1.75σ , and a flavor composition measurement shown in Fig. 2 where for the first time the 1σ contours close inside the parameter space [14].

Using an algorithm to find Double Pulses, two searches on 7.5 years of data found two candidates each, one of which in common [16, 17]. These exclusive searches for tau neutrinos were not sensitive to other flavors, and neither spectral index nor flavor composition was fit. Despite

Figure 3: The tau neutrino candidate common to all presented analyses. *Left*: Detector view: The grey circles mark the reconstructed Double Cascade vertex positions with the neutrino direction indicated with the grey arrow. The light pattern collected on select optical modules alongside reconstruction predictions are shown in the insets. From [9]. *Right*: 2-d image and saliency map for one string: Measured light level vs. DOM number and time (*top*) with two leading edges of light visible near DOMs 26 and 27; the saliency (*bottom*), *i.e.* the magnitude of the gradient of the CNN score, with red (blue) regions indicating where increased (decreased) light would increase one of the CNN scores and overlaid contour showing the pixels where the light level went to zero and roughly tracing the light level plot above. Adapted from [18].

of the major sources of systematic uncertainty is the modeling of photon propagation in the South Pole ice (see [22] for the most recent ice model), which itself is limited by the available calibration devices [23]. The IceCube-Upgrade [24] is being deployed this 2025-2026 season. Primarily designed to improve IceCube’s capabilities to measure oscillation parameters with atmospheric neutrinos, the Upgrade also includes many new calibration devices for the South Pole ice. The new ice model will be applied to all available data, and previously taken data will be reprocessed to reflect the evolving understanding of our detector response.

In the next decade, IceCube aims to extend the instrumented in-ice volume with IceCube-Gen2, expected to collect ~ 5 times more high-energy (tau) neutrinos. Alongside better identification methods, and the improved understanding of the ice optical properties, IceCube-Gen2 may be sensitive to detect a change in neutrino flavor composition as a function of energy [8].

5 Summary

Tau neutrinos remain the least studied Standard Model particles. The small neutrino cross-sections call for large instrumented volumes, while the short tau lifetime requires dense instrumentation. Those requirements are difficult to achieve simultaneously. Despite its sparse detector layout, the IceCube collaboration successfully detected astrophysical tau neutrinos using a variety of methods, with the evidence exceeding a significance of 5σ . The measured flavor composition is compatible with neutrinos being produced via pion decay at sources, and we are starting to constrain some source production mechanisms (e.g. the production via neutron decay is constrained at $> 2\sigma$).

IceCube has a unique sample of tau neutrinos in the energy range of $\mathcal{O}(100 \text{ TeV}) - \mathcal{O}(\text{PeV})$, far beyond energies reachable with man-made accelerators.

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